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● New record of *Oedichirus astoni* (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae: Paederinae) in Chongqing

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● 阿氏梨须隐翅虫在重庆的分布新纪录

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The genus *Oedichirus* Erichson, 1839 belongs to the subtribe Procirrina (Pinophilini) with *Oedichirus paederinus* Erichson, 1840 as its type species. Up to present, the genus *Oedichirus* comprises 398 species, among them, 17 species were recorded from China (Assing 2013, 2014, 2019; Li *et al.* 2015; Rougement 2018; Li *et al.* 2019; Duan *et al.* 2024).

Before this study, distribution records of *Oedichirus astoni* Rougement, 2017 are restricted to Hong Kong and Shenzhen, Guangdong (Rougement 2017; Xu *et al.* 2020). The present record from Chongqing represents an update to the inland distribution of this species.

Morphological observations and the aedeagus dissection were conducted under a stereomicroscope (Olympus SZ2-ILST). Habitus, diagnostic features, as well as measurements were taken using a digital stereomicroscope (KEYENCE-VHX-5000), then modified, annotated, and grouped to plates using Adobe Photoshop 2021. All Chinese common names are translated literally after the Latin names. Labels of type material are cited verbatim. The material used in this study is deposited in the personal collection of the corresponding author.

Genus *Oedichirus* Erichson, 1839 梨须隐翅虫属

Remarks. The morphological characteristics of the genus *Oedichirus* were precisely defined and easily recognized by the following characters: (1) spiniform pencil of antennomere 11; (2) the abdominal segments IV to VI have windows in the intersegmental membrane adjacent to the tergite and sternite; (3) most of tergite and sternite VII fused together except for the apical incision, (4) humeral angle of elytra without long seta laterally (Duan *et al.* 2024).

FIGURE 1. A Habitus of *O. astoni* B Aedeagus in dorsal view C Aedeagus in lateral view D Aedeagus in ventral view E Sternite VIII in male F Habitat of *O. astoni* in Qingmuguan Town. Scale bar = 1 mm for A; scale bar = 0.5 mm for B–E.

***Oedichirus astoni* Rougemont, 2017 阿氏梨须隐翅虫**

Figs 1, 2

Oedichirus astoni Rougemont, 2017: 270; Xu *et al.* 2020: 141; Duan *et al.* 2024: 384.

Type locality. “Wang Tong, Lantau, HK” [香港横塘大屿山]

Material examined. 1 ♂, “CHINA, Chongqing: Shapingba District [中国重庆市沙坪坝区], Qingmuguan Town [青木关镇], Xiaoluchi [小鹿池]” // “alt. 506m 2026.I.9, Tian-Xuan Gu leg.”

Distribution. China: Chongqing (new municipal record), Guangdong, Hong Kong.

Comment. This species is quite similar to *Oedichirus chapmani* Hayashi, 1989, which is distributed in China, Japan, Bangladesh, India, Thailand, Laos and Vietnam, but can be distinguished by the following characteristics: the 6th visible abdominal sternum is black (red in *O. chapmani*); the punctures on the pronotum are sparser, with two rows of asymmetrical punctures on the middle and posterior parts; and the ventral process of the aedeagus is slender and curved towards the apex.

Most species of the genus *Oedichirus* in China have been recorded in the coastal provinces of the east and south. The present discovery from Chongqing represents the first record of the genus in this municipality. As the collection site is adjacent to farmland and near human settlements (Fig. 1F), the species might have been introduced accidentally through human activities. However, considering the small size of the farmland patch, the well-preserved state of the surrounding primary forests, and the limited survey effort for this species, the possibility that this site represents part of its native distribution cannot be excluded. In any case, this new record from Chongqing significantly extends the known distribution range of the genus in China.

FIGURE 2. Distribution map of *O. astoni*.

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